

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Supporting Children in Preschool Years

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based approach to supporting children in the preschool years

CotN_Preschool_Report_1.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **High quality early years provision is crucial to child development.** It is key for developing language, social, emotional and physical skills and good behaviour.
- **There is a crisis in preschool early years and childcare provision.** There is a lack of places, financial instability, recruitment and retention difficulties and a pressing need for upskilling the workforce.
- **One in three children are not ready for school.** There is an alarming rise in childhood development delays, notably in speech and language development.
- **Children from the most deprived areas are particularly at risk from the crisis in provision.** They are 18.5 percentage points behind children from the least deprived areas on the Early Years Foundation Stage (EYFS) profile.
- **National level focus:**
 - Focus on investment in early childhood programmes; support improvement and extension of training for professionals and families; join systems up through better sharing of information.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Develop partnerships integrating health, education and care services; integrate data sets to identify need; develop provision around holistic support for families and with parental involvement; develop local training and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) support.
 - Build on programmes such as Nuffield Early Language, Natural Thinkers, ONE programme, 50 Things to do Before Your Five, Sheffield Small Talk.

The Problem: There is a Crisis in Autism Support and Assessment

Nurseries have closed, there is financial instability, recruitment and retention difficulties and a pressing need for training and CPD of the workforce. Only 17% of early years staff receive job related CPD training. But early years provision is crucial to successful child development. It lays the foundations of good language, social, emotional and physical skills and good behaviour.

“We have heard many concerning experiences of teachers and other school and social work professionals of children arriving at Reception wearing nappies, still sitting in buggies and unable to properly communicate or socialise with other children.”

1 in 3 children are not ready for school

They are six times more likely to need SEND support

Half of these perform below expected level at Key Stage 1

They are 2.5 times more likely to be absent from school

What you can do at a local level

- **Prioritise early childhood education, especially in disadvantaged areas.** The most disadvantaged children benefit most from early years education. This benefits them, their families and society.
- **Integrate services across health, education and social care sectors.** The key is to provide a holistic approach this includes valuing play, relationship building, care and physical activity.
- **Develop data sharing systems and base local provision on detailed needs analysis.** This helps with early identification of problems, and development of and access to services.
- **Provide and extend access to training for professionals and parents.** High quality early years education depends on highly developed understanding child development and how to: integrate education and care, work with children and families, and develop home and school literacies. Evidence shows, for example, how home visits by trained professionals and positive parenting programmes leads to better outcomes.
- **Co-produce services with families.** This can result in better identification of needs, better service design and better outcomes.
- **Promote awareness of early years schooling.** 20% of three to four year olds were not registered for the 30 hour entitlement in 2024.
- Develop the kinds of programmes highlighted below.

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Nuffield Early Language Intervention (NELI) Pre-school	20-week programme for children aged three to four years. Aims to boost the language skills of children and better prepare them for school entry. Combines universal enrichment with targeted small group and individual sessions for children with poor language skills. NELI Pre-school comprises training for nursery practitioners, oral language assessment, intervention, and whole-class instruction.	More inclusive school environments that support autistic children and families and lead to better educational, health and social outcomes.
Natural Thinkers	A service which aims to promote children's communication and language development, wellbeing, and involvement through the provision of high-quality outdoor learning and play.	Improved children's wellbeing and involvement scores.
50 Things to do Before You're Five	Provides ideas for fun, low or no-cost activities for families with young children. Aims to help children develop the skills, language, and resilience needed for starting school and beyond. It can also be used by nurseries, childminders, schools, health teams, cultural settings, and community organisations, or anyone who wants to improve outcomes for young children.	Improved communication between parents and children, improved relationships with parents and increased engagement of children.
Sheffield Small Talk	Speech and language therapy clinic, providing inclusive no-cost provision for all preschool children with SEND.	Access to specialist services and support and improved speech and language.
The ONE Programme	The Orchestrating Numeracy and the Executive (ONE) programme has been developed to support children's mathematics learning in nursery with an aim to reduce socioeconomic attainment gaps that start to emerge during this time.	Improved mathematical understanding and long-term improvement in attainment.